

OPEN LETTER

[version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

Network for forest by-products charcoal, resin, tar, potash (COST Action EU-PoTaRCh) [version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

Magdalena Zborowska ¹, Jakub Brózdowski¹, Jakob Starlander ², Jiri Woitsch ³, Erika Ribechini⁴, Rodica-Mariana Ion⁵, Oliver Nelle⁶, Koen Deforce^{7,8}, Anna Varga⁹, Péter Szabó^{10,11}, Elena Badea ¹², Johannes Tintiner-Olifiers¹³, Katja Tikka ¹⁴, Jeannette Jacqueline Lucejko⁴

¹Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology, Poznań University of Life Sciences, Poznań, 60-637, Poland

²Universität Bern, Bern, 3012, Switzerland

³Institute of Ethnology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Praha, 11000, Czech Republic

⁴Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry, University of Pisa, Pisa, 56124, Italy

⁵National Institute of Research and Development for Chemistry and Petrochemistry - ICECHIM, Bucharest, 060021, Romania

⁶Landesamt für Denkmalpflege im Regierungspräsidium Stuttgart, Gaienhofen-Hemmenhofen, 78343, Germany

⁷Ghent University, Gent, 9000, Belgium

⁸Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels, 1000, Belgium

⁹Padon Foundation, Budapest, 1088, Hungary

¹⁰Institute of Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Pruhonice, 25243, Czech Republic

¹¹Department of Environmental Studies, Masaryk University, Faculty of Social Studies, Brno, 60200, Czech Republic

¹²University of Craiova, Craiova, 200585, Romania

¹³Denkstatt - denkstatt GmbH, Wien, 1140, Austria

¹⁴University of Helsinki, Helsinki, 00014, Finland

V1 First published: 13 Aug 2024, 4:176
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18160.1>

Latest published: 17 Oct 2024, 4:176
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18160.2>

Abstract

COST Action EU-PoTaRCh establishes a network focused on the past, present and future use of the major forest by-products in Europe. The Action emphasizes forest by-products, mainly potash, tar, resin, and charcoal (PoTaRCh), as representatives of the traditional heritage of forest exploitation, including extractives used along the time for their specific chemical, biological activity and therapeutic effect. The scientific objective of the Action is to demonstrate the value of these products for the communities and their socio-economic growth, as

Open Peer Review

Approval Status ? ✓

1

2

version 2

(revision)

17 Oct 2024

version 1

13 Aug 2024

view

view

well as their impact on biodiversity and climate throughout time. The general aim is to identify and assess changes in production and use of PoTaRCh and extractives, along with their social and environmental impacts on sustainable development, and draw lessons for the future based on this legacy. In this way, the Action supports the sustainable use of forests and the transfer of knowledge about circular economy practices, as a contribution to the systemic shift to the new circular bio-economy.

A key component of the Action is to support stakeholders that are knowledgeable about PoTaRCh goods and are interested in them because they are used in production, education and promotion of our natural and cultural heritage. The Action meets a wide range of demands thanks to the participation of partners with various activity profiles (museums, state forests, forest industry, tradition bearers associations, tourism industry, etc.). The EU-PoTaRCh Action highlights three COST inclusivity policies: the participation of inclusivity Target Countries with a long history of developing PoTaRCh, a special emphasis on gender balance, and the involvement of young researchers in leadership positions.

Plain Language Summary

COST Action EU-PoTaRCh has established a network dedicated to exploring the past, present, and future use of major forest by-products in Europe. This initiative highlights key forest by-products, specifically potash, tar, resin, and charcoal (PoTaRCh), as important elements of traditional forest exploitation heritage. These products have been valued over time for their unique chemical and biological properties, as well as their therapeutic effects.

The scientific goal of the Action is to demonstrate the value of these products to communities, showcasing their role in socio-economic growth and their impact on biodiversity and climate over the ages. The general aim is to identify and assess changes in the production and use of PoTaRCh and other extractives, along with their social and environmental impacts on sustainable development. By understanding this legacy, we can draw lessons for the future.

In doing so, the Action supports the sustainable use of forests and promotes knowledge about circular economy practices, contributing to the systemic shift towards a new circular bio-economy.

A key component of the Action is supporting stakeholders who are knowledgeable about PoTaRCh goods and interested in their use for production, education, and the promotion of our natural and cultural heritage. The Action meets a wide range of demands by involving partners with diverse activity profiles, including museums, state forests, the forest industry, tradition bearers' associations, and the tourism industry.

1. **Diego Tamburini** , The British Museum, London, UK

2. **Anna Sandak**, InnoRenew CoE Livade, Izola, Slovenia
University of Primorska, Glagoljaška, Slovenia

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

The EU-PoTaRCh Action emphasizes three COST inclusivity policies: the participation of Inclusivity Target Countries with a rich history of developing PoTaRCh, a special focus on gender balance, and the involvement of young researchers in leadership positions.

Keywords

Cultural heritage, history, archaeology, forest by-products, bio-economy, chemical composition, physical properties

This article is included in the [Forest and Forestry Sciences gateway](#).

This article is included in the [COST Actions gateway](#).

Corresponding authors: Magdalena Zborowska (magdalena.zborowska@up.poznan.pl), Jeannette Jacqueline Lucejko (jeannette.lucejko@unipi.it)

Author roles: **Zborowska M:** Conceptualization, Project Administration, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Brózdowski J:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing; **Starlander J:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Woitsch J:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ribechini E:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ion RM:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Nelle O:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Deforce K:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Varga A:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Szabó P:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Badea E:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Tintiner-Olifiers J:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Tikka K:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Lucejko JJ:** Conceptualization, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Framework Programme for Research & Innovation as part of the COST Action CA22155 Network for forest by-products charcoal, resin, tar, potash as supported by the COST Association (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2024 Zborowska M *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Zborowska M, Brózdowski J, Starlander J *et al.* **Network for forest by-products charcoal, resin, tar, potash (COST Action EU-PoTaRCh) [version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 1 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2024, 4:176 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18160.1>

First published: 13 Aug 2024, 4:176 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18160.1>

EU-PoTaRCh: Celebrating and Innovating Forest By-Products

COST Action EU-PoTaRCh weaves a dynamic network focused on the timeless and evolving uses of Europe's key forest by-products: potash, tar, resin, and charcoal (PoTaRCh). These natural treasures, rooted in traditional forest practices, are celebrated for their unique chemical, biological, and therapeutic properties.

The initiative's scientific mission is to showcase how these by-products have historically fueled community growth, enhanced economic vitality, and impacted biodiversity and climate. By tracing their journey from past to present, EU-PoTaRCh aims to understand their social and environmental roles, promoting sustainable development and learning valuable lessons for the future. This endeavor champions the principles of a circular bio-economy, where resources are reused and recycled.

Central to EU-PoTaRCh is the support for stakeholders who are passionate about PoTaRCh products and their cultural heritage. These include experts involved in production, education, and promotion. The Action brings together a rich tapestry of partners—museums, state forests, the forest industry, tradition bearers, and the tourism sector—to meet diverse needs and foster collaboration.

The initiative also prioritizes inclusivity by engaging countries with a rich history of PoTaRCh development, ensuring gender balance, and promoting young researchers in leadership roles. By embracing these principles, EU-PoTaRCh not only preserves the legacy of forest by-products but also drives innovation and sustainability, enhancing cultural and economic resilience across Europe.

Potash, tar, resin, and charcoal (PoTaRCh) are four materials closely linked in their materiality, of extraordinary importance for societal resource use and the most significant products of non-timber forest use in Europe. (Figure 1). The production of these materials is partly overlapping and intrinsically linked. All these products, including the extractives such as tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols etc, are potentially important resources in the context of renewable materials and bio-economy. Understanding the diverse production methods from the past, along with their positive and negative impacts on societies and environments across different regions of Europe since prehistory, is crucial. This knowledge will not only support the current preservation of (bio)cultural heritage but also inform future strategies for sustainable raw material supply.

Figure 1. Symbols of potash, tar, resin, charcoal and logo of EU-PoTaRCh Action doi:[10.18150/O75Y0C](https://doi.org/10.18150/O75Y0C).

To date, no comprehensive research has been conducted across the natural, social, applied, and humanities sciences on PoTaRCh to fully understand the scale and impact of its production on communities and societies, its significance for the natural environment, and its relevance to the current economy on a continental or even global scale. Consequently, there has been a grassroots need among scientists, tradition bearers, museum professionals, producers, and association representatives, to initiate a COST Action to address this challenge. In this article, we are pleased to celebrate and introduce the COST Action EU-PoTaRCh¹.

COST inclusiveness policies in EU-PoTaRCh

Steps towards successful COST inclusiveness policies have already been implemented. To date, EU-PoTaRCh includes partners from 30 COST member countries, including 17 Inclusion Target Countries (ITCs), as well as partners from Mexico, Morocco and South Africa. ITC representatives constitute 57% of our members. The Action has achieved gender balance, with a similar participation rate of men and women, despite the topic traditionally being male-dominated. We are also actively working to attract young researchers, whose participation is a priority for EU-PoTaRCh, as the initiative is primarily addressed to them (Figure 1). Our success is evident in the fact that our network includes 163 academic institutions in Europe and around the world, which guarantees broad, deep and multi-faceted PoTaRCh research. (Figure 2).

Building the capacity of EU-PoTaRCh

EU-PoTaRCh sets itself ambitious tasks aimed at expanding the network and building the potential of the Action²:

- Mentoring and promotion of young people, especially from ITCs, where there are many active tradition bearers. Young people can easily combine research with practice.
- Creating an interdisciplinary collaborative network brings together excellence in history, archaeology, natural sciences and technology across Europe to support joint research on forest by-products to expand and exchange knowledge and experiences.
- Establishing a network on the future prospects of PoTaRCh for the bioeconomy and forest transformation. The White Paper for policy-makers and international organizations will be an important outcomesupporting the innovation potential of European society.
- Creating opportunities for interdisciplinary cooperation between scientists, practitioners (tradition bearers) museums, and enterprises in the field of bioeconomy, forest transformation and tourism.
- Facilitating the creation of a network of museums, associations of active tradition bearers, communities and other stakeholders, leading to the preparation of a European plan for the protection of the tangible and intangible heritage of PoTaRCh.

Figure 2. 1st General Meeting of Network for forest by-products charcoal, resin, tar, potash (COST Action EU-PoTaRCh), 5-7 March, 2024, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Prague Czech Republic.

- Disseminating knowledge and experiences resulting from EU PoTaRCh activities among the general public through publications (reports and articles), workshops, conferences, an easily accessible, user-friendly website, social media and other media appearances.

The above objectives are pursued through various activities organized within the Action:

- We arrange meetings, workshops, and conferences that cater to all Action members, focusing closely on EU PoTaRCh deliverables. These activities may target specific groups (e.g., individual working groups) or involve all Action members.
- Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSM) grants, Inclusion Target Countries Conference (ITC) grants and Dissemination Conference (DC) grants are available for all Action members to apply for. These initiatives aim to foster international collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- Training schools provide intensive education on EU-PoTaRCh at host institutions' headquarters. These schools primarily benefit young researchers from across Europe, although participation is open to all interested individuals.
- We also organize webinars where every EU PoTaRCh member can present their ideas, research, experiences, projects, or opinions.
- We initiate, help in organizing and finding partners for joint research, scientific projects, publications, popularization and promotional activities or dissemination of knowledge about PoTaRCh. Additionally, we provide financial support for open access publications..

All these efforts promote cooperation, networking, knowledge sharing, and research and development within the framework of the EU PoTaRCh Action.

Description of the Working Groups in EU-PoTaRCh

All objectives of the EU-PoTaRCh Action are implemented within the activities of five Working Groups (WGs) each focusing on different approaches to the past, present, and future of PoTaRCh, all strongly interconnected and unified under the heritage aspect². WG 1 compiles detailed definitions of traditional skills, knowledge, and technologies, along with their current applications. WGs 2, 3, and 4 represent various scientific approaches: laboratory analytics, archaeology, and environmental history, respectively. Finally, WG 5 evaluates future perspectives. (Figure 3).

The production processes of PoTaRCh materials show both similarities and differences that have not yet been fully identified and described at European level, including their areas of application. These processes can be traced thanks to archaeological research and historical written sources. Their survival is primarily ensured by local producers (especially in ITC and outside Europe), non-governmental organizations and associations dealing with the protection of intangible cultural heritage. Therefore objectives of WG1 (HERITAGE) are:

- Identification of cultural heritage related to PoTaRCh,
- Develop and implement measures to protect both tangible (historical places of production) and intangible (traditional knowledge) cultural heritage related to PoTaRCh at European level,
- Promoting the PoTaRCh heritage and ensuring its preservation for the future, while strengthening the social and economic position of the tradition bearers,
- Identification of PoTaRCh-related measures and policies that can benefit the tourism industry as well as local and regional development.

The characterization of PoTaRCh materials enables the identification of their chemical and structural composition, monitoring

Figure 3. Network of Working Groups connections UE-PoTaRCh doi:10.18150/O75Y0C.

of compositional changes over time, detection of decomposition products, and analysis of interactions with environmental factors such as soil. This detailed understanding offers extensive opportunities to determine the sources and types of raw materials for PoTaRCh production, production conditions and methods, and storage and usage methods. Consequently, this knowledge allows for a comprehensive interpretation of PoTaRCh's impact on communities, the economy, and the environment on both regional and global scales. Therefore WG2 (ANALYTICAL CHARACTERIZATION) works with:

- Exploration the origins and traditional technologies by compositional analysis of PoTaRCh materials,
- Exploration of chemical/analytical approaches to characterize PoTaRCh materials based on analytical and archaeological chemistry as well as both organic and inorganic material characterization,
- Developing methodological approaches (including methods able to provide information on the biological origin of natural materials, technological and possible anthropogenic modifications) and analytical protocols as well as defining new research questions based on literature review, current production and experiments.

The production of charcoal and tar has left significant traces in the soil across many European cultural landscapes, while the production of potash is more challenging to trace archaeologically and often survives only in field names. Despite significant research identifying and assessing historical production sites, there is a lack of coordinated research at the European level. Therefore, WG3 (ARCHAEOLOGY) focuses on:

- Identifying the archaeological remnants of PoTaRCh production sites in the soil ("soil monuments"),
- Designing and implementing a standardized methodological approach for data exploration, validation, and characterization across Europe,
- Identifying and documenting the presence and absence of PoTaRCh sites and complexes in European cultural landscapes, while also understanding the contributing factors.

The environmental history of PoTaRCh, including the relationship between the environment, society, sustainable development and the socio-ecological system along with related changes from the local to the global level, remains largely unknown. The production technology of PoTaRCh is influenced, among other factors, by natural conditions. PoTaRCh production technology

has not yet been systematically compared on a local to European scale within the context of the natural environment. Therefore, WG4 (ENVIRONMENTAL HISTORY) has the following task:

- Reconstruct and investigate the short- and long-term consequences of PoTaRCh production and use on socio-ecological systems in Europe and beyond,
- Identify human and non-human actors, examine knowledge transfer among producers and across different fields, investigate transportation and mobility aspects, and political and economic dimensions to promote sustainable management of natural resources,
- Compare PoTaRCh production technologies on various scales, from local to European.

COST Action EU-PoTaRCh asks the question: how can PoTaRCh products contribute to global challenges related to reducing reliance on fossil carbon sources? There are a few renewable sources of chemicals that can effectively compete with fossil sources, and PoTaRCh products represent a potentially promising alternative. WG5 (FUTURE PERSPECTIVE) explores

how trade in forest by-products can meet global challenges, facilitated by the following tasks:

- Assessing the future economic prospects of the PoTaRCh heritage,
- Defining current and potential future products and methods relevant to the bioeconomy,
- Highlighting potential threats and challenges stemming from tradition and history

Conclusions

We anticipate that in the coming years, the COST EU PoTaRCh Action will represent a significant milestone in the extensive history of PoTaRCh products. However, realizing this goal hinges entirely on the dedication and active involvement of current and prospective Action members. We hope that this article has inspired you to consider joining us in fostering a broader and more resilient network for PoTaRCh.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

References

1. [For more information about COST. Reference Source](#)
2. [For more information about COST Action CA22155. Reference Source](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 11 September 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.19629.r43523>

© 2024 Sandak A. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Anna Sandak

¹ InnoRenew CoE Livade, Izola, Livade, Slovenia

² University of Primorska, Glagoljaška, Koper, Slovenia

Dear authors, please find my comments below

Abstract and Plain Language Summary provide the same information. Most of the sentences are repeated. Is there a reason for having both?

You wrote: *"COST Action EU-PoTaRCh weaves a dynamic network focused on the timeless and evolving uses of Europe's key forest by-products: potash, tar, resin, and charcoal (PoTaRCh). These natural treasures, rooted in traditional forest practices, are celebrated for their unique chemical, biological, and therapeutic properties"*.

I'm not sure if I understand correctly the author's intention - what do you mean by the celebration of potash, tar, resin, and charcoal?

Please standardize the grammatical style of the WG1 objectives. Currently, three different styles are being used: "identification..., develop..., promoting...". Choose one of these styles for consistency. The same applies to WG2, and it may be beneficial to maintain a uniform style across all WGs.

Double check the paragraph that introduces WP5, some words are mended

You stated that *"EU-PoTaRCh not only preserves the legacy of forest by-products but also drives innovation and sustainability, enhancing cultural and economic resilience across Europe"*, which is very ambitious. This COST action has been active for almost one year but I'm sure you already faced some challenges. I've prepared a few questions that may guide further discussion and reflection related to four aspects:

Identified Barriers and Mitigation Strategy: Have you encountered significant barriers that could impede progress toward the COST action objectives? If so, what strategies are in place to mitigate these challenges?

Innovation and Sustainability: How specifically will this COST action drive the innovation and

sustainability you mentioned? Are there particular areas or technologies where you see the most potential?

Contribution to the Circular Bio-Economy: What is the planned approach to supporting the development of a circular bio-economy? How does EU-PoTaRCh intend to influence this transition, particularly through the use of forest by-products?

Informing Future Strategies: How will this initiative contribute to the development of future strategies for sustainable raw material supply? Are there any key outputs or learnings that could shape future policy or industrial practices?

I hope these questions will stimulate further discussion and refine the project's direction as it continues to evolve.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Partly

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Yes

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: wood science and technology, material science

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 30 August 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.19629.r43528>

© 2024 **Tamburini D.** This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Diego Tamburini

The British Museum, London, England, UK

The open-letter “Network for forest by-products charcoal, resin, tar, potash (COST Action EU-PoTaRCh) by Zborowska et al. presents the objectives and activities of this COST Action in a good way. The authors summarise the scope and relevance of the Action and promote the activities related to it in a convincing way. I find the letter mostly well-written and organised and I only have few suggestions to possibly improve its quality.

The Abstract and Plain Language Summary only include the aims of the COST action, but not much on the plans to achieve these aims. These are described later, but probably mention this in the abstract would make it more complete.

A few additional suggestions for the abstract/summary:

Extractives could probably be replaced by “plant extractives” to make it clearer

“along the time” does not sound the most appropriate here. Similarly, in the plain language summary, terms like “over the ages” are quite vague. The abstract also does not give a sense of the chronological scale that the research intends to cover. This should be clarified.

Communities are mentioned, but which communities? This part can be better written. “their” also refers to different things, making the reading confusing.

“impact on biodiversity and climate throughout time.” This is slightly obscure at this point. Also “throughout time” is not the most appropriate here.

The authors distinguish between the “scientific objective” and the “general aim”. I found it slightly confusing. Why is one scientific and the other general?

Terms like tradition/traditional are also used. I would encourage the authors to be careful about this or maybe try and find a way to define what they mean by tradition/traditional. It tends to get a sense of something that belongs to the past and has not changed, as opposed to modern “non-traditional” practices, but all this can be quite controversial and heritage institutions are trying to avoid this term. “Tradition bearers” is also used and I wonder if there is an alternative to this term. Some of the above comment also apply to the main text. This is generally clear and gives a better sense of the intentions and activities of the action. A few points follow.

While I agree that “no comprehensive research has been conducted across the natural, social, applied, and humanities sciences...” some research is indeed available albeit not comprehensive. I would probably tone down this sentence. Generally, it would also be nice to mention an example of this topic being researched and conclusions being helpful to address the challenges presented, even if at a smaller scale of course.

“despite the topic traditionally being male-dominated.” Is there evidence for this? It sounds slightly forces as it is presented now.

“as the initiative is primarily addressed to them (Figure 1).” I don’t see how Figure 1 refers to young researchers. Maybe this is a typo?

Some of the aims listed in “Building the capacity of EU-PoTaRCh” section feel slightly repetitive. For example, 2 and 4, but also some of the others. I wonder if these could be presented in a stronger way. Also, I think there is some confusion between objectives and activities. Some activities are presented in the objectives.

Some language issues are present in the description of WG2, especially around the bullet points.

The three bullet points also sound very similar to me. Could these be combined in a single point or maybe two?

“Global” is often used throughout the article, but the focus being Europe, is global really appropriate in this context? European scale is sometimes mentioned and I found it more appropriate.

The actions and activities of WG5 remain slightly vague. This part of the article could possibly be strengthened, maybe with an example? The sentence “There are a few renewable sources of chemicals that can effectively compete with fossil sources, and PoTaRCh products represent a potentially promising alternative.” could be expanded on. What few renewable sources of chemicals are the authors referring to? How are PoTaRCh products promising? Maybe referring to some already available research on this could be helpful to strengthen the argument.

I think generally the letter could benefit from some bibliographical references putting it in context a bit more.

The bullet points of WG5 are quite vague too.

The conclusions could be strengthened too, maybe summarising the key messages of the Action.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

No

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: I am an analytical chemist working on the characterisation and identification of organic materials in a cultural heritage context. I felt like I could assess all parts of the letter.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 20 Sep 2024

Magdalena Zborowska

Review Diego Tamburini *Dear Reviewer, Thank you very much for your reviews of the article, I hope that the changes introduced will improve its value and make it more accessible to readers. On behalf of authors, Magdalena Zborowska* The open-letter "Network for forest by-products charcoal, resin, tar, potash (COST Action EU-PoTaRCh) by Zborowska et al. presents the objectives and activities of this COST Action in a good way. The authors summarise the scope and relevance of the Action and promote the activities related to it in a convincing way. I find the letter mostly well-written and organised and I only have few suggestions to possibly improve its quality.

Comment: The Abstract and Plain Language Summary only include the aims of the COST action, but not much on the plans to achieve these aims. These are described later, but probably mention this in the abstract would make it more complete. A few additional suggestions for the abstract/summary:

Extractives could probably be replaced by "plant extractives" to make it clearer
"along the time" does not sound the most appropriate here. Similarly, in the plain language summary, terms like "over the ages" are quite vague. The abstract also does not give a sense of the chronological scale that the research intends to cover. This should be clarified.
Answer: Abstract has been improved according to suggestions.

Comment: Communities are mentioned, but which communities? This part can be better written. "their" also refers to different things, making the reading confusing.
"impact on biodiversity and climate throughout time." This is slightly obscure at this point. Also "throughout time" is not the most appropriate here.
Answer: Text has been improved according to suggestions.

Comment: The authors distinguish between the "scientific objective" and the "general aim". I found it slightly confusing. Why is one scientific and the other general?
Answer: Text has been improved according to suggestions

Comment: Terms like tradition/traditional are also used. I would encourage the authors to be careful about this or maybe try and find a way to define what they mean by tradition/traditional. It tends to get a sense of something that belongs to the past and has not changed, as opposed to modern "non-traditional" practices, but all this can be quite controversial and heritage institutions are trying to avoid this term.
Answer: The term "traditional" is deeply ingrained in the subject matter of EU-PoTaRCh, and it is challenging to describe phenomena and actions without using it, even if it is not fully defined. However, the authors have removed the term where its inclusion was not essential and where its removal did not alter the meaning of the sentence.

Comment: "Tradition bearers" is also used and I wonder if there is an alternative to this term.
Answer: A more precise term might be "promoters/advocates/lovers of tradition." However, "tradition bearer" is a well-established term with universal recognition. Despite its awkwardness, we have retained it in certain places in the text where it is most appropriate.
Some of the above comment also apply to the main text. This is generally clear and gives a

better sense of the intentions and activities of the action. A few points follow.

Comment: While I agree that “no comprehensive research has been conducted across the natural, social, applied, and humanities sciences...” some research is indeed available albeit not comprehensive. I would probably tone down this sentence. Generally, it would also be nice to mention an example of this topic being researched and conclusions being helpful to address the challenges presented, even if at a smaller scale of course.

Answer: The purpose of the article was to outline the goals of the Action, describe our approach, and explain the rationale, without delving into the current state of knowledge. Given the broad scope of the Action, it is challenging to select literature from such diverse scientific areas without favoring a particular field, which we aimed to avoid in this overview article. As part of the Action, we plan to develop several review publications focused on different areas of interest as defined by the working groups. These reviews will be supported by a comprehensive range of literature sources.

Comment: “despite the topic traditionally being male-dominated.” Is there evidence for this? It sounds slightly forced as it is presented now.

It is not forced. It is true that the Action, thanks to our efforts, manages to maintain gender balance. What is more, the scientific community is also represented by both sexes. One producer community, ... is represented mainly by men.

Answer: While the EU-PoTaRCh Action has made strides in maintaining gender balance within the scientific community, we recognize that the situation is different outside of it. Specifically, in sectors such as production and among tradition bearers and association members, there is a predominance of men. Given that one of the core principles of all COST Actions is to promote gender balance, we believe it is important to address this imbalance in non-scientific environments as well. Our articles aim to highlight our efforts to address this issue and accurately reflect the current gender disparities. Therefore, we will use the term that best describes the existing situation.

Comment: “as the initiative is primarily addressed to them (Figure 1).” I don’t see how Figure 1 refers to young researchers. Maybe this is a typo?

Answer: Of course it is mistake. We rejected this information in text.

Comment: Some of the aims listed in “Building the capacity of EU-PoTaRCh” section feel slightly repetitive. For example, 2 and 4, but also some of the others. I wonder if these could be presented in a stronger way.

Answer: Thank you for your feedback. The points do indeed overlap and differ mainly in nuances. As a result, I combined points 4 and 5 without compromising the clarity of the text. Points 2 and 4 address different objectives: point 2 focuses on networking among scientific disciplines, while point 4 pertains to networking in non-scientific environments. Therefore, I have kept these two points separate.

Comment: Also, I think there is some confusion between objectives and activities. Some activities are presented in the objectives.

Answer: Thank you for your observation. We appreciate your attention to the distinction between objectives and activities. While certain goals are indeed achieved through specific actions—such as using training schools and STSMs to mentor and promote young researchers, and organizing

meetings, workshops, and conferences to foster interdisciplinary cooperation—this approach is central to the COST Action. For this reason, we prefer to keep the text as is. However, we will ensure that the distinction between objectives and activities is made clear where possible.

Comment: Some language issues are present in the description of WG2, especially around the bullet points. The three bullet points also sound very similar to me. Could these be combined in a single point or maybe two?

Answer: Thank you for your comment, in fact the last point contains the above, so it can be deleted.

Comment: “Global” is often used throughout the article, but the focus being Europe, is global really appropriate in this context? European scale is sometimes mentioned and I found it more appropriate.

Answer: You're right that the term “global” can be challenging. While it is easier to focus on Europe, where most of our members are based, we cannot overlook the global nature of the issues related to PoTaRCh. Environmental changes, such as those affecting the climate due to PoTaRCh production, have global implications. Similarly, historical economic and social changes—such as PoTaRCh production in Europe and Africa and its subsequent trade in the United States—were global in scope. Despite having less detailed knowledge about other continents compared to Europe, we will strive to study PoTaRCh on a global scale because it is a topic with worldwide relevance.

Comment: The actions and activities of WG5 remain slightly vague. This part of the article could possibly be strengthened, maybe with an example? The sentence “There are a few renewable sources of chemicals that can effectively compete with fossil sources, and PoTaRCh products represent a potentially promising alternative.” could be expanded on. What few renewable sources of chemicals are the authors referring to? How are PoTaRCh products promising? Maybe referring to some already available research on this could be helpful to strengthen the argument.

Answer: Thank you for comment. As we mentioned previously, we try not to quote other articles in this article, it is only intended to provide general information about the campaign, encouraging you to look for more information on the website or in review articles.

Comment: I think generally the letter could benefit from some bibliographical references putting it in context a bit more.

Answer: We have already explained our idea.

Comment: The bullet points of WG5 are quite vague too.

The conclusions could be strengthened too, maybe summarising the key messages of the Action.

Answer: Thank you for your valuable feedback. While we believe the bullet points in WG5 are specific and align with the objectives of the Action, we understand that they might seem somewhat unclear. We will review them to ensure they are more precise and effectively convey the intended details. Additionally, we will work on strengthening the conclusions by summarizing the key messages of the Action to provide a clearer and more impactful overview.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider

whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions? No Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.